

1 **NOD1 signaling in embryonic stem cells during lineage commitment to the TE.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We report here biologically significant
9 NOD1 signaling in embryonic stem cells during lineage commitment to the TE.

10 Citations

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